

THE FATTY OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *PRINSEPIA UTILIS*, ROYLE.

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The chemical and physical constants of the fatty oil (21%) from the seeds of *Prinsepia utilis*, Royle as well as of its constituent acids have been determined. No constituent of medicinal value has been located in the oil.

Prinsepia utilis, Royle (N.O. Rosaceae) known as *bhekal* (Hind.) is a deciduous, thorny shrub found in the outer Himalayas, from Hazara to Bhutan at 2,000 to 9,000 ft. It also occurs in Khasia Hills and is naturalized in the Nilgiris. The fruit is 0.5"—0.7" long, cylindrical, fleshy and deep purple when ripe and has one seed. By expression the seeds yield a fatty oil which is much used in the N. W. Himalayas for food, illumination and as a medicine.

Except for the statement made by Kirtikar and Basu ("Indian Medicinal Plants," 1st Ed., Pt. I, p. 521) that "In specific gravity, iodine value and melting point of the insoluble fatty acids, the oil (two samples at Indian Museum) resembles that derived from cotton seed", there is no reference in literature to the physical and chemical properties of the oil. It was, therefore, thought advisable to record the results of the detailed examination of the oil in this paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The air-dried seeds (received from the Divisional Forest Officer, Chakrata Forest Division, Chakrata, U. P.) were found to consist of 37.5% pericarp and 62.5% kernels. The latter on hot expression in a hydraulic press yielded 18% of a pale yellow fatty oil. Additional 19.2% were obtained by extraction of the residual cake with petroleum ether thus making a total of 37.2%.

TABLE I.
Chemical and physical constants.

		Fatty oil		Mixed acids	
Consistency	... Thin	Sap. value	200.2	Mean M. W.	... 272.3
Rotation $[\alpha]_D^{30}$	... Nil	Acid value	23.1	Iodine value (Hanus)	... 112.0
Sp. gr. at 20°	... 0.9215	Acetyl value	12.3	Sat. acids	... 21.3%
Ref. index at 20°	... 1.4625	Hehner value	89.3	Unsat. acids	... 77.2%
Iodine value* (Hanus)	... 109.8	Unsapon. matter	0.5%	Resin acids	... 1.5%

* On standing the oil got oxidised and in course of a year the iodine value fell to 84.0.

Composition of the Mixed Acids.

The oil (285 g.) was saponified with alcoholic sodium hydroxide. The alcohol was distilled off, the resultant soap dissolved in water and the mixed acids liberated by the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The free fatty acids were washed with warm water and neutralised with 10% sodium hydroxide. The soap solution was concentrated, incorporated with washed filter paper pulp and the resulting mass was dried, powdered, and extracted with ether in a Soxhlet to remove the unsaponifiable matter. The mixed acids (204 g.) were liberated from the residual soap, purified in the usual manner and 147.5 g. of these were separated into solid and liquid acids by the well known Twitchell's lead salt-alcohol method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

TABLE II.

	Acids	Net wt.	I. V.
(S)	Solid	28.70	2.3
(S)	Solid	5.58	31.6
(L)	Liquid	111.20	142.3
(R)	Resin	2.02	—
		147.50	

Solid Acids (S).

The solid acids (44 g. *) were converted into methyl esters in the usual manner with 3% methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid. After distilling off the methyl alcohol the esters were washed with saturated salt solution, 5% sodium carbonate and finally with distilled water. After drying under vacuum 42 g. of the esters were distilled at 9 mm. into the following fractions.

TABLE III.

Fractions.	B. p.	Mean M. W.	Net wt.	Component methyl esters			
				Myristate.	Palmitate.	Stearate.	Lignocerate.
S ₁	Below 185°	240.1	0.75	0.75	—	—	—
S ₂	185°—188°	268.2	3.10	—	3.10	—	—
S ₃	188°—191°	270.0	14.50	—	14.50	—	—
S ₄	191°—193°	276.5	8.84	—	6.79	2.05	—
S ₅	193°—199°	280.8	5.60	—	3.44	2.16	—
S ₆	199°—205°	283.4	3.29	—	1.72	1.57	—
S ₇	205°—210°	298.2	3.52	—	—	3.52	—
Residue	—	—	2.40	—	—	0.40	2.00
		Total	42.00	0.75	39.55	9.70	2.00
		Per cent	100%	1.8%	70.3%	23.1%	4.8%

* A portion was taken from a separate Twitchell's separation.

All these fractions were saponified separately, the corresponding acids were liberated and these were fractionally crystallised from acetone in order to isolate the individual acids in the usual manner.

Acids from fraction S_1 had a mean M. W. of 226.1 and melted at 50-51°. The acid, therefore, appears to be myristic. The quantity being small no further identification was possible.

Acids from fraction S_2 (m.p. 58-59°, mean M. W. 259) and S_3 (m.p. 58-59°, mean M. W., 258.6) being alike were mixed together and crystallised from dilute acetone. Crystals, m.p. 61-62°, M. W. 258, were obtained. Their mixed melting point with an authentic sample of palmitic acid remained unaltered. The residue from the mother-liquor melted at 59-60° and had a M. W. of 260. The fractions thus almost entirely consisted of palmitic acid.

Acids from fractions S_4 and S_5 were separately obtained and fractionally crystallised from acetone. Products melting at 57-58° and 56-57° and having M. W. 262.5 and 266.8 were obtained. Further crystallisation did not bring about separation of any acid but gave the same product, m.p. 54-55°, M. W. 269. This was presumably the eutectic mixture of palmitic and stearic acid since palmitic acid was found in fraction S_3 and stearic in fraction S_6 .

Acids from fraction S_6 had a melting point of 58-59° and M. W. of 269.4. Crystallised from acetone crystals melting at 66-67° (mixed m.p. with pure stearic acid 67-68°) and M. W. 278.2 were obtained. The fraction thus contains stearic acid (isolated) and palmitic acid (not isolated).

Acids from fraction S_7 melted at 64-65°. Their mixed melting point with a sample of pure stearic acid was 64-66°. Twice crystallised from alcohol they melted at 68-69°, M. W. 284.2. Their mixed melting point with pure stearic acid remained unaltered. The acids from the mother-liquor melted at 64-65°, M. W. 280.0. The acids from this fraction consisted almost entirely of stearic acid.

The acids from the residue being mixed with the products of decomposition were highly coloured. These were first saponified and the liberated acids were thrice crystallised from dilute acetone giving crystals, m.p. 75-76°, M. W. 358.4. When mixed with a pure sample of lignoceric acid the melting point was 77-78°. The acid thus appeared to be lignoceric acid. The residue from mother-liquor on concentration and crystallisation yielded crystals melting at 64-65°, M. W. 310.9. Mixed m.p. with pure stearic acid was 64-67°. The residue, therefore, appeared to consist of lignoceric and stearic acids.

Solid Acids (S).

These acids were liberated from the lead salts that had crystallised out on standing from the lead salts of liquid acids after the latter's separation by Twitchell's method. They were oxidised according to the method of Bertram (*Zeit. deut. oel fett Ind.*, 1925, 48, 733) to remove the unsaturated acids. The resulting saturated acids (M. W. 245) on crystallising twice from dilute acetone gave a product, m.p. 58-59°, M. W. 259. Its mixed melting point with pure palmitic acid was 61-63°. From the filtrate a product melting at 50-51° presumably myristic acid was isolated but was not sufficient for further identification. These solid acids, therefore, consisted of a mixture of myristic, palmitic and unsaturated acids identified below.

Liquid Acids (L).

Oxidation.—The liquid acids were saponified to break up any esters which might have been formed during Twitchell's separation. A portion of the de-esterified acids was converted into potassium soap and oxidised in cold alkaline solution with dilute potassium permanganate according to the modified method of Hazura (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes", 1921, 6th Ed., Vol. I, p. 575). From the resultant acids dihydroxystearic acid, m.p. 130-31°, M. W. 315, a tetrahydroxy stearic acid (sativic acid) m.p. 172-75°, M. W. 352, and azeleic acid, m.p. 101-102°, M. W. 186.5, were isolated. No hexahydroxystearic acid was found indicating thereby the absence of linolenic acid.

Bromination.—Liquid acids (2.6502 g.) were brominated according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch, *loc. cit.* p. 585) yielding 3.9200 g. of the brominated product but no hexa or higher bromides. The product was soluble in petroleum ether and no crystalline tetrabromide could be isolated on concentrating and cooling the solution. This showed that the terabromides present were mostly from β -linoleic acid. The oxidation and the bromination results thus clearly showed that the liquid acids consisted only of oleic and linoleic acids.

The above data on calculation gave the percentages of the constituent acids as follows: myristic (1.8%), palmitic (15.2%), stearic (4.5%), lignoceric (0.9%), oleic (32.6%), linoleic (43.6%) and resin (1.4%). It may be pointed out here that the mixed fatty acids exhibit the general characteristics of the mixed acids from the seed fats of Rosaceae family (Hilditch, "The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", 1940, p. 134) in that the major

component acids are oleic and linoleic and the minor ones palmitic and stearic though palmitic acid occurs in quantity much larger than has so far been found in the family and oleic acid in quantity much smaller.

Unsaponifiable Matter.

The unsaponifiable matter, obtained from the sodium soaps of the mixed acids by extraction with ethyl ether, when crystallised from alcohol gave plates, m.p. 127-28°. On recrystallisation from the same solvent crystals melting at 128-29° were obtained. The acetyl derivative of the product melted at 118-19°. The product gave the usual tests for phytosterol and appeared to be sitosterol, the common phytosterol found in seed fats.

C O N C L U S I O N.

The fatty oil from the seeds of *Prinsepia utilis*, Royle, consists of the glycerides of myristic acid (1·8%), palmitic acid (15·2%), stearic acid (4·5%), lignoceric acid (0·9%), oleic acid (32·6%) and linoleic acid (43·6%) together with resin acid (1·4%) and unsaponifiable matter (0·5%), containing the sterol, sitosterol. There is nothing out of the ordinary in the composition of the oil to explain its supposed medicinal properties. It might, however, be said that the oil belongs to the semi-drying class and can be used for edible purposes and in soap making.

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